

checkCIF/PLATON report

Structure factors have been supplied for datablock(s) op-8-31

THIS REPORT IS FOR GUIDANCE ONLY. IF USED AS PART OF A REVIEW PROCEDURE FOR PUBLICATION, IT SHOULD NOT REPLACE THE EXPERTISE OF AN EXPERIENCED CRYSTALLOGRAPHIC REFEREE.

No syntax errors found. CIF dictionary Interpreting this report

Datablock: op-8-31

Bond precision:	C-C = 0.0151 A	Wavelength=1.54184	
Cell:	a=51.542(3)	b=22.7187(10)	c=19.7112(9)
	alpha=90	beta=90	gamma=90
Temperature:	140 K		
	Calculated	Reported	
Volume	23081(2)	23081(2)	
Space group	P b c n	P b c n	
Hall group	-P 2n 2ab	-P 2n 2ab	
Moiety formula	2(C30 H24 B2 Co F10 N6 O6), C20 H40 K O8, C12 H24 K O6 [+ solve]	C72 H72 B4 Co2 F20 K N12 O18, C20 H40 K O8	
Sum formula	C92 H112 B4 Co2 F20 K2 N12 O26 [+ solvent]	C92 H112 B4 Co2 F20 K2 N12 O26	
Mr	2421.24	2421.23	
Dx, g cm ⁻³	1.394	1.394	
Z	8	8	
Mu (mm ⁻¹)	3.814	3.814	
F000	9984.0	9984.0	
F000'	9989.67		
h,k,lmax	61,27,23	61,27,23	
Nref	20386	20373	
Tmin,Tmax	0.196,0.842	0.086,1.000	
Tmin'	0.080		

Correction method= # Reported T Limits: Tmin=0.086 Tmax=1.000
AbsCorr = GAUSSIAN

Data completeness= 0.999 Theta(max)= 66.600

R(reflections)= 0.1376(12314) wR2(reflections)= 0.3998(20373)

S = 1.049 Npar= 1518

The following ALERTS were generated. Each ALERT has the format

test-name_ALERT_alert-type_alert-level.

Click on the hyperlinks for more details of the test.

Alert level B

PLAT084_ALERT_3_B High wR2 Value (i.e. > 0.25) 0.40 Report

Author Response: The overall quality of the model is pretty poor because the samples were very sensitive and they decomposed quite easily.

PLAT341_ALERT_3_B Low Bond Precision on C-C Bonds 0.01513 Ang.

Author Response: The model displays disordered moieties and this explains why the precision of some C-C bond lengths is quite low.

Alert level C

RINTA01_ALERT_3_C The value of Rint is greater than 0.12

Rint given 0.153

PLAT020_ALERT_3_C The Value of Rint is Greater Than 0.12 0.153 Report

PLAT082_ALERT_2_C High R1 Value 0.14 Report

PLAT234_ALERT_4_C Large Hirshfeld Difference F2 --C3 . 0.20 Ang.

PLAT234_ALERT_4_C Large Hirshfeld Difference C4 --C5 . 0.20 Ang.

PLAT234_ALERT_4_C Large Hirshfeld Difference O20 --C82 . 0.17 Ang.

PLAT234_ALERT_4_C Large Hirshfeld Difference O21 --C84 . 0.17 Ang.

PLAT234_ALERT_4_C Large Hirshfeld Difference O25 --C93 . 0.19 Ang.

PLAT234_ALERT_4_C Large Hirshfeld Difference C85 --C86 . 0.19 Ang.

PLAT234_ALERT_4_C Large Hirshfeld Difference C94 --C95 . 0.25 Ang.

PLAT234_ALERT_4_C Large Hirshfeld Difference C98 --C99 . 0.18 Ang.

PLAT241_ALERT_2_C High 'MainMol' Ueq as Compared to Neighbors of C89 Check

PLAT241_ALERT_2_C High 'MainMol' Ueq as Compared to Neighbors of C95 Check

PLAT241_ALERT_2_C High 'MainMol' Ueq as Compared to Neighbors of C100 Check

PLAT242_ALERT_2_C Low 'MainMol' Ueq as Compared to Neighbors of C5 Check

PLAT242_ALERT_2_C Low 'MainMol' Ueq as Compared to Neighbors of K2 Check

PLAT242_ALERT_2_C Low 'MainMol' Ueq as Compared to Neighbors of C99 Check

PLAT411_ALERT_2_C Short Inter H...H Contact H10D ..H55B . 2.09 Ang.

x,1-y,1/2+z = 7_566 Check

PLAT906_ALERT_3_C Large K Value in the Analysis of Variance 3.872 Check

PLAT906_ALERT_3_C Large K Value in the Analysis of Variance 2.850 Check

PLAT911_ALERT_3_C Missing FCF Refl Between Thmin & STh/L= 0.595 11 Report

Alert level G

PLAT002_ALERT_2_G Number of Distance or Angle Restraints on AtSite 29 Note

PLAT003_ALERT_2_G Number of Uiso or Uij Restrained non-H Atoms ... 30 Report

PLAT042_ALERT_1_G Calc. and Reported MoietyFormula Strings Differ Please Check

PLAT063_ALERT_4_G Crystal Size Possibly too Large for Beam Size .. 0.61 mm

PLAT072_ALERT_2_G SHELXL First Parameter in WGHT Unusually Large 0.17 Report

PLAT083_ALERT_2_G SHELXL Second Parameter in WGHT Unusually Large 106.72 Why ?

PLAT176_ALERT_4_G The CIF-Embedded .res File Contains SADI Records 3 Report

PLAT178_ALERT_4_G The CIF-Embedded .res File Contains SIMU Records 2 Report

PLAT186_ALERT_4_G The CIF-Embedded .res File Contains ISOR Records 2 Report

PLAT301_ALERT_3_G Main Residue Disorder(Resd 1) 20% Note

PLAT301_ALERT_3_G Main Residue Disorder(Resd 2) 4% Note

PLAT606_ALERT_4_G Solvent Accessible VOID(S) in Structure ! Info

PLAT790_ALERT_4_G	Centre of Gravity not Within Unit Cell: Resd. # C30 H24 B2 Co F10 N6 O6		2	Note
PLAT794_ALERT_5_G	Tentative Bond Valency for Co1 (III)	.	3.13	Info
PLAT794_ALERT_5_G	Tentative Bond Valency for Co2 (III)	.	3.17	Info
PLAT860_ALERT_3_G	Number of Least-Squares Restraints		469	Note
PLAT909_ALERT_3_G	Percentage of I>2sig(I) Data at Theta(Max) Still		42%	Note
PLAT910_ALERT_3_G	Missing # of FCF Reflection(s) Below Theta(Min).		2	Note
PLAT978_ALERT_2_G	Number C-C Bonds with Positive Residual Density.		0	Info

0 **ALERT level A** = Most likely a serious problem - resolve or explain
2 **ALERT level B** = A potentially serious problem, consider carefully
21 **ALERT level C** = Check. Ensure it is not caused by an omission or oversight
19 **ALERT level G** = General information/check it is not something unexpected

1 ALERT type 1 CIF construction/syntax error, inconsistent or missing data
13 ALERT type 2 Indicator that the structure model may be wrong or deficient
12 ALERT type 3 Indicator that the structure quality may be low
14 ALERT type 4 Improvement, methodology, query or suggestion
2 ALERT type 5 Informative message, check

It is advisable to attempt to resolve as many as possible of the alerts in all categories. Often the minor alerts point to easily fixed oversights, errors and omissions in your CIF or refinement strategy, so attention to these fine details can be worthwhile. In order to resolve some of the more serious problems it may be necessary to carry out additional measurements or structure refinements. However, the purpose of your study may justify the reported deviations and the more serious of these should normally be commented upon in the discussion or experimental section of a paper or in the "special_details" fields of the CIF. checkCIF was carefully designed to identify outliers and unusual parameters, but every test has its limitations and alerts that are not important in a particular case may appear. Conversely, the absence of alerts does not guarantee there are no aspects of the results needing attention. It is up to the individual to critically assess their own results and, if necessary, seek expert advice.

Publication of your CIF in IUCr journals

A basic structural check has been run on your CIF. These basic checks will be run on all CIFs submitted for publication in IUCr journals (*Acta Crystallographica*, *Journal of Applied Crystallography*, *Journal of Synchrotron Radiation*); however, if you intend to submit to *Acta Crystallographica Section C* or *E* or *IUCrData*, you should make sure that full publication checks are run on the final version of your CIF prior to submission.

Publication of your CIF in other journals

Please refer to the *Notes for Authors* of the relevant journal for any special instructions relating to CIF submission.

PLATON version of 18/09/2020; check.def file version of 20/08/2020

